

Fluctuations in Turtle Nesting in the Batu Hiu Beach Conservation Area: A 2015–2025 Review

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Abstract

Batu Hiu Beach in West Java serves as a nesting site for sea turtles, particularly for olive ridley, hawksbill, and green turtles. This study reviews habitat characteristics and nesting trends over the past decade. Key factors influencing nesting include beach width, slope, sand texture, vegetation cover, and human disturbance. While the area retains suitable physical features, declining nesting activity suggests increasing pressure from habitat changes and anthropogenic threats. Strengthening community-based conservation is essential to support future turtle populations.

Keywords: sea turtle, nesting habitat, Batu Hiu Beach, conservation, coastal environment

Introduction

Sea turtles are widespread throughout Indonesia, including Java. West Java has three primary turtle landing sites: Sindangkerta, Pangumbahan, and Pangandaran. Pangandaran has been designated a Marine Conservation Area through Decree No. 1 of 2022 of the Minister of Maritime Affairs and Fisheries of the Republic of Indonesia, covering an area of 38,810.15 hectares. This designation aims to preserve the turtle habitat in the area (Ministry of Maritime Affairs and Fisheries of the Republic of Indonesia, 2022).

One of Pangandaran's nesting sites is Batu Hiu Beach, located in Ciliang Village, Parigi District. On this beach, the community, through the Raksa Bintana Foundation, independently manages a turtle conservation center, which currently houses three species of turtles: olive ridley, hawksbill, and green turtles (Damayanti & Junianto, 2023). Unfortunately, the trend of turtle landings on this beach continues to decline, with the last reported arrival in 2022. This decline is thought to be related to human activities such as fishing and low conservation awareness, reinforced by the discovery of turtle carcasses along the beach (Nurfitrhani et al., 2024).

In addition to human disturbance, the decline in nesting activity is also influenced by habitat conditions. Turtles are known to be highly faithful to the beaches where they previously laid their eggs (Ubaydillah et al., 2023), but they are also capable of moving if habitat conditions deteriorate (Dermawan et al., 2009; Oliveira et al., 2020). The oceanographic dynamics of Batu Hiu Beach, which borders directly on the Indian Ocean, also influence the beach's physical characteristics such as width, slope, sand texture, and shoreline stability. High-energy waves can alter the shoreline, ultimately affecting the slope and nesting area (Rupilu, 2020).

Global sea turtle populations continue to decline, with some species even threatened with extinction. In the wild, hatchlings face threats from natural predators such as crabs and birds. However, the greatest disturbance comes from humans, particularly through coastal development that reduces nesting areas (Ario et al., 2016). Furthermore, sea turtles, particularly green turtles, are hunted for their highly valuable meat and shells. In Bali, green turtle meat is one of the most consumed foods due to its large size and high meat yield (Isdianto et al., 2022; Pradana et al., 2013).

Natural factors such as increased wave height, temperature changes, and shifting shorelines also influence nesting success. Flooding from storms can cause egg mortality, and sand temperature determines the sex of hatchlings. Research shows that hatching temperatures below 29°C tend to produce male hatchlings, while temperatures above this temperature tend to produce females (Turnip et al., 2020). Isdianto et al., 2022; Suastika & Suprpti, 2012). The beach slope is too steep due to abrasion, which also makes it difficult for turtles to reach the nesting area (Rupilu et al., 2019).

Turtle Habitat Suitability

Although six of the world's seven turtle species are found in Indonesia, not all coastal areas are suitable for their nesting. Turtles only select locations that meet specific ecological requirements. Habitat suitability analysis aims to assess a location's suitability to support the turtle's life cycle, particularly in terms of reproduction. According to Nurbaeti (2016), several important parameters in this analysis include:

Beach width:

Ideally, it should be between 20 and 80 meters. Beaches that are too narrow make it difficult for turtles to nest, while beaches that are too wide drain their energy when returning to the sea (Azhari et al., 2023; Hendrastuti et al., 2018).

Beach slope:

Turtles prefer beaches with a gentle slope (<30°) to facilitate access to the nesting zone. However, high humidity due to water intrusion can increase the risk of fungal and bacterial infections (Mansula & Romadhon, 2020; Siahaan et al., 2020).

Sand texture:

Fine sand is preferred because it makes nest digging easier. The ideal sand content is ≥90% (Ibrahim et al., 2016; Nurbaeti, 2016).

Coastal vegetation:

Protects nests from predators, flooding, and excessive heat. Vegetation reduces direct radiation to the sand, thus maintaining a stable incubation temperature (Nurbaeti, 2016).

Nighttime lighting:

Turtles are sensitive to artificial light, especially blue-green light (500–520 nm). Ideal lighting values range from 0 to 3 lux (Salmon, 2003; Santos et al., 2006).

Percentage of buildings: Buildings contribute to visual and sound disturbances that can hinder turtles from climbing to the beach (Putra et al., 2023).

Availability of feeding areas:

Although it does not directly affect egg-laying, the availability of food plays an important role in the health of mother turtles and hatchlings (Nurbaeti, 2016).

Turtle Landing Conditions

The Batu Hiu Beach Turtle Conservation Area is managed by the Raksa Bintana Foundation, an independent private foundation. This hatchery recovers turtle eggs that land around Batu Hiu Beach, which encompasses the entire coast of Pangandaran Bay.

The eggs are hatched in semi-natural nests, and the hatchlings are cared for until they are ready to be released into the ocean.

Figure 1. Turtle Egg Laying Data in Pangandaran Regency

Based on data recorded by the Raksa Bintana Foundation, turtle landing activities in recent years have shown significant fluctuations, as seen in the graph above. Over a 10-year period (2015-2024), the total number of mother turtles laying eggs was 31, with an average of 3.1. The highest number of nestings occurred in 2024, with 8 turtles. By June 2025, 5 turtles had laid eggs. This number is better than the previous turtle landings up to 2016. This condition indicates a positive development that can support an increase in the number of turtles laying eggs compared to 2024.

This condition is also reflected at Batu Hiu Beach, the focus of this study. The research was conducted in the Batu Hiu Beach Turtle Conservation Area, with boundaries extending from Batu Hiu Hill westward to the Pangandaran Harbor Pier. The coastline in this study area is approximately 4.73 km long. Data on the number of turtle nests in this area can be seen in Figure 2.

Picture 2. Turtle Egg Laying Data on Batu Hiu Beach

Based on Figure 2, there is a fluctuation in the number of turtle landings from year to year in the Batu Hiu Beach area. Landing and nesting activities *in* turtles are crucial physiological and ecological processes, where female individuals will dig holes on the beach, lay dozens to hundreds of eggs, and then return to the sea (Hamann et al., 2010).

Within a 10-year period (2015-2024), the total number of mother turtles that laid eggs was 17, with an average of 1.7. The highest number of egg-layings occurred in 2016 with 4 turtles. From 2015 to 2018, the number of egg-layings that occurred was in the range of 2-4 turtles per year, but no egg-layings were recorded in 2019 and 2023. This activity increased again in 2024, and by mid-2025 (June), two turtles had been recorded landing to lay eggs. This number has exceeded the annual average of turtle landings in the last ten years, and it is expected that this positive trend will continue until the end of 2025.

Sea turtles exhibit a high degree of fidelity to the beaches where they previously nested, so they are likely to return to the same location in the next nesting season (Ubaydillah et al., 2023). Therefore, nest site selection is strongly influenced by the physical characteristics of the beach, such as slope, width, sand substrate texture, and the presence of vegetation (Pfaller et al., 2009).

More than half of the turtle egg-layings recorded by the Raksa Bintana Foundation originated from the study site. This demonstrates the potential of Batu Hiu Beach as a turtle nesting location. Several factors support nesting activity, including a quiet environment, the absence of light, and the absence of movement that could disturb the turtles' approach to the beach. If human activity disrupts the turtles' nesting activities, they will seek out other coastal areas deemed safe for nesting. (Longdy, 2002) The favorable physical characteristics of Batu Hiu Beach, such as its wide beach, coastal vegetation that generally provides shade for turtle nests, relatively fine sand texture, and a moderate slope, make this area a potential habitat for turtle landing and nesting activities. In some locations, there is also dense vegetation that turtles prefer for laying eggs.

Summary

This literature review explores the nesting conditions of sea turtles at Batu Hiu Beach, Pangandaran, West Java, which lies within a designated Marine Conservation Area. The study focuses on habitat suitability, nesting trends, and threats to sea turtle populations. Three turtle species—olive ridley, hawksbill, and green turtle—are found in the area, managed by a local conservation group, Yayasan Raksa Bintana. Despite the physical characteristics of the beach being generally favorable—such as wide, gently sloping shores, fine sand, and vegetation cover—nesting activity has shown fluctuations, with a significant decline in certain years. This decline is attributed to both natural factors (e.g., wave energy, shoreline shifts, and temperature changes) and human activities (e.g., coastal development, artificial lighting, bycatch, and turtle hunting). The document highlights the importance of maintaining suitable physical beach conditions and minimizing disturbances to support sustainable turtle nesting. It also stresses the role of local conservation efforts in protecting this critical habitat.

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